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IAS Academic Corner - Case 1

ACL Reconstruction with Double Level Valgization Osteotomy

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Abstract

Chronic ACL deficiency is known to lead to meniscal tears and medial compartment arthritis. Arthroscopic ACL reconstruction combined with high tibial osteotomy has become the standard of care for patients with associated varus deformity. However in cases of severe varus deformity arising from both femur and tibia, high tibial osteotomy alone leads to increased joint line obliquity. This ultimately leads to shear stress in the joint. In this case report we describe a patient with combined ACL deficiency and a varus deformity of 12° who underwent a double level osteotomy and acl reconstruction. The surgical technique and review of literature has been described

Case report

A 50-year-old male presented to outpatient department with complaints of pain, locking from and occasional instability in his left knee. He gives a history of fall bike twelve years back. On clinical examination, he had a varus deformity of lower limbs and quadriceps wasting of the left lower limb. The range of motion was full and medial joint line tenderness was present on palpation. Anterior drawer test and Lachman test were grade 3 positive. He was further investigated with a scannogram and MRI. The radiographs revealed early arthritic changes in the medial compartment and a varus of 12°. The calculation of angles on the scannogram showed MPTA of 80.5°, LDFA of 91°, JLCA of 2.3° and JLO of 3.6°. MRI scan of the left knee showed a chronic ACL tear and a medial meniscus bucket handle tear. After discussing the pros and cons, patient was suggested arthroscopic ACL reconstruction with a double level osteotomy to correct the varus deformity.

Planning of the osteotomy

The double level osteotomy was planned on the picture archiving and communication system. Planning revealed a lateral distal femoral closing wedge osteotomy with wedge of 6.9mm and medial opening wedge proximal tibial osteotomy with a wedge of 8mm.

Surgical technique

Using standard arthroscopy portals, diagnostic arthroscopy was completed. Medial meniscus rolled out bucket handle tear was identified and partial meniscectomy was done with a meniscal punch. ACL femoral tunnel of size 8mm diameter and 18mm length was drilled using a 6mm offset guide in an anatomical position. A standard lateral approach was taken to expose the distal femur. The osteotomy was marked with the help of k wires aiming to reach just above the adductor tubercle. A biplanar osteotomy of the femur was done and a hinge of around 1cm was left intact at the medial cortex. 7mm wedge of bone was removed. The osteotomy was closed gradually under c arm guidance and fixed with a locking plate. Notch view was taken to make sure that there were no screws crossing the intercondylar notch. The arthroscope was reinserted and a screw was found to be inside the ACL femoral tunnel. It was exchanged with a smaller screw. A standard medial approach was done to expose the proximal tibia. The superficial mcl was released while keeping the distal attachment intact. The osteotomy was marked with the hinge point kept at the tip of the fibula approximately 1.5cm below the articular surface. The starting point of the osteotomy was 4cm below the joint line medially. A biplanar medial opening wedge osteotomy was performed with an opening of 8mm. It was fixed with a precontoured locking HTO plate. The wedge of bone removed from the femur was inserted in the tibial osteotomy. Next the arthroscope was reinserted and a tibial tunnel was drilled using the standard ACL jig kept at 50°. Hamstring ACL graft was passed and fixed with adjustable endobutton on femoral side and bioscrew on tibial side. Wound wash was given and closed in layers over drain.

Postoperative rehabilitation

A toe touch weightbearing protocol is followed for 6 weeks followed by full weight bearing. Knee range of motion is started on pod 1. A standard ACL rehabilitation protocol is followed. Weight resisted training is started at 12 weeks.

Review of literature

To the best of our knowledge, there are no papers in the literature describing the technique or results after a combined double level osteotomy and ACL reconstruction. There are many studies describing combined high tibial osteotomy and ACL reconstruction. In high tibial osteotomies, there is a limit in the amount of wedge that can be opened. The postoperative MPTA cannot exceed 94° as excessive MPTA can lead to more joint line obliquity. A high joint line obliquity induces shear stress in the joint and produces inferior results of the osteotomy³. The preoperative planning revealed a deformity both in the femur and tibia. So it is imperative to correct the varus in both femur and tibia to prevent excess JLO.

Mabrouk A et al⁴ described the results of double level osteotomy in long term followup of 58 cases in a single center. The mean age of their population was 47.9 ± 9.8 years. The mean followup was 10.8 ± 3 years. The mean varus deformity was $12.7 \pm 3.9^{\circ}$. 77.6% of the patients had KL grade ≥ 3 . They found significant improvement in all patient related outcome measures. 8-year survivorship of the double level osteotomy was 97.1%. the 10-year survivorship was 94.4%. 5.2% of cases were converted to arthroplasty at an average of 5.9 ± 3.1 years.

Abs A et al⁵ compared the results of double level osteotomy and HTO at a mean followup of 3.6 ± 1.3 years. There were 38 high tibial osteotomy patients and 31 double level osteotomy patients. They concluded that the double level osteotomy results in a more physiologic JLO and slightly improved Ucla and patient satisfaction scores.

Conclusion

A combined double level osteotomy and ACL reconstruction is a good option in patients with combined tibial and femoral varus deformity and ACL deficiency.

Figure 1: Evaluation and planning of double level osteotomy

- a) Preoperative varus deformity of 12° . b) LDFA (lateral distal femoral angle) of 91° .
 c) MPTA (medial proximal tibial angle) of 80.5° . d) existing and desired Mikulicz line.
 e) Femoral wedge calculation. f) tibial wedge calculation

Figure 2: Osteotomy and fixation

a) K wire insertion for lateral distal femoral closing osteotomy.

b) femoral osteotomy after 7mm wedge removal.

c) c arm image showing alignment rod passing through the center of the knee after tibial medial opening high tibial osteotomy.

d) postoperative AP radiograph showing well fixed double level osteotomy.

e) postoperative lateral radiograph showing maintained posterior slope.

f) 6 weeks postoperative radiograph showing Mikulicz line passing through the lateral tibial spine

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